

been found that minimal inhibition concentration (MIC) decreases with increasing molecular weight.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Saurashtra University and to Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre for providing research facilities. We are also thankful to U.G.C. for providing research scholarship to (N.A.L.).

References

1. T. S. GARDNER, E. WENIS and F. A. SMITH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5455.
2. E. GRUNBERG, R. J. SCHNITZER, B. LEIWANT, I. L. D'ASCENSIO and E. TITSWORTH, *Quart. Bull. Sea View Hosp.*, 1952, **13**, 8.
3. A. G. KARLSON and W. H. FELDMAN, *Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1953, **68**, 75.
4. J. BERNSTEIN, W. P. JAMBOR, W. A. LOTT, F. PANSY, B. A. STEINBERG and H. L. YALE, *Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1953, **67**, 354.
5. O. ISLER, H. GUTMANN, O. STRAUB, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1955, **38**, 1039.
6. F. McMILLAN, F. LEONARD, R. I. METTZER and J. A. KING, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1953, **42**, 457.
7. H. H. FOX and G. T. GIBAS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 994; 1955, **20**, 60; 1956, **21**, 256.
8. W. W. OUTHBERSTON and J. J. MOFFATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 561.
9. F. H. SCURD, J. K. LANDQUIST and F. L. ROSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 154.
10. E. OIORANESCH, *Rev. Chem. (Bucharest)*, 1954, **5**, 425.
11. C I B A Ltd., B. P., 1956, 74071.
12. JENSCH, U. S. P. 2092552.

Preparation of β -aryl, γ -aroyl Butyric Acids : the Attempted Synthesis of Hydantoin Analogues

B. B. GHATGE, S. N. KULKARNI and A. N. KADAM
National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-8, India

Manuscript received 27 June 1977, revised 3 May 1980,
accepted 5 November 1980

HENZ and Leslie¹ have synthesised a number of 5,5-disubstituted hydantoin from ketones by Bucherer-Berg reaction. Even though they synthesised β -(5-aryl hydantoin 5-) propionic acid from acrylophenone, Deshpande and Nargund² described a shorter route to β -(5-aryl hydantoin 5-) propionic acids starting from β -aroyl propionic acids and also reported their activity as antituberculosis agents. Analogous to this, synthesis of β -aryl γ -(5-aryl hydantoin 5-) butyric acids were attempted. Hence the preparation of β -aryl γ -aroyl butyric acids were taken up as intermediate compounds.

Earlier many workers^{3,4,5} have reported the synthesis of simple β -phenyl γ -benzoyl butyric acid by

different methods, synthesis of β -aryl, γ -aroyl butyric acids having substituents in aromatic rings have not been reported. In the present investigation, procedure for β -aryl, γ -aroyl butyric acids is standardised and fifteen new γ -keto acids are reported (Table 1).

TABLE I

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R	I		II	
				m.p.°C	Yield%	m.p.°C	
1.	H	H	H	57.0°	35.9	155.0	
2.	H	H	CH ₃	—	—	102.0	
3.	H	CH ₃	H	96°	97.4	133.0	
4.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	92.0	
5.	H	OCH ₃	H	77-78 ¹⁰	32.7	124.0	
6.	H	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	89.5	
7.	H	Cl	H	103-104 ¹¹	27.9	158.0	
8.	H	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	132.0	
9.	CH ₃	H	H	74.0°	39.7	164.5	
10.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	—	—	131.0	
11.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	127.5°	41.2	122.0	
12.	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	78.0	
13.	CH ₃	OCH ₃	H	94.0°	35.2	105.0	
14.	CH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	67.5	
15.	CH ₃	Cl	H	122.5 ¹²	26.1	137.0	
16.	CH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	95.0	
17.	OCH ₃	H	H	106.0 ¹³	41.5	149.0	
18.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	—	—	104.0	
19.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	126.0 ¹⁴	37.2	126.0	
20.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	97.5	
21.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	101-102 ¹⁵	29.4	137.0	
22.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	111.5	
23.	OCH ₃	Cl	H	121.0 ¹⁶	24.3	127.0	
24.	OCH ₃	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	94.5	
25.	Cl	H	H	101 ¹⁷	26.8	143.0	
26.	Cl	H	CH ₃	—	—	116.0	
27.	Cl	CH ₃	H	165 ¹⁸	25.5	132.0	
28.	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	113.5	
29.	Cl	OCH ₃	H	130 ¹⁶	26.1	138.0	
30.	Cl	OCH ₃	CH ₃	—	—	108.0	
31.	Cl	Cl	H	134 ¹⁶	21.2	156.0	
32.	Cl	Cl	CH ₃	—	—	129.0	

Note : All the compounds have given satisfactory C, H and Cl (wherever required) analysis. The analyses were carried out at NCL (Microanalysis Group), Pune-8.

Various chalcones⁶(I) were prepared having different substituents in both the aromatic rings at para positions and subjected to Michael addition of diethyl malonate (ME). The resulting diesters were hydrolysed, without purification and decarboxylated to obtain β -aryl, γ -aroyl butyric acids(II). They were identified by elemental estimation and infrared spectroscopy (aromatic carbonyl: 1685 cm⁻¹-1665 cm⁻¹, carboxyl carbonyl: 1720 cm⁻¹-1705 cm⁻¹)⁷ and confirmed by preparing their esters which are also identified by their elemental analysis (Table 1). The acids were subjected to Bucherer-Berg reaction but failed to yield hydantoin derivatives(III) (Fig. 1). More polar solvents and changed reaction conditions was also a failure. Cause of non-formation of five membered hydantoin ring may be the steric hindrance of bulky β -aromatic substitution,

Fig. 1

Experimental

(II) β -Aryl- γ -Aroyl-Butyric Acid :

A mixture of KOH (0.657 g, 0.012 M), diethyl malonate (4.2 g, 0.03 M), ethanol (1 ml), ether (10 ml) were placed in a 250 ml round bottom flask, equipped with a dropping funnel, a mechanical stirrer and a cooling bath. The mixture was stirred at 15° and chalcone⁶ (0.015 M) in 100 ml of ether was added dropwise over 1 hr. It was further stirred for additional 2.5 hrs at room temperature. Then the mixture was acidified with dil. HCl and the ether layer was separated. The residue after removing the solvent was diluted with KOH solution (5.3 g in 10 ml of H₂O) to give deformed mass, which was heated on steam bath for 2 hrs (10 ml of water was added at the end of 1 hr). It was then cooled under tap and conc. H₂SO₄ (9 g in 12 ml of H₂O) was added slowly (cracking noise and white ppt.). The mixture was heated on steam bath for 3 hrs, cooled under tap and extracted with saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (30 ml). The heterogeneous aqueous layer after acidification gave white ppt. which was recrystallized from boiling water.

References

1. H. R. HENZ and R. E. LESLIE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 602.

2. R. W. DESHPANDE and K. S. NARGUND, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 1043.
3. A. MICHAEL and J. ROSS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1632.
4. VORLANDER and KNOTZSCH, *Ann.*, 1897, 294, 332.
5. D. S. BRESLOW and C. R. HAUSER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2385.
6. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text-book of Practical Chemistry*, p. 681.
7. Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds J. R. Dyer, p. 34 (Ed. 1971).
8. CLAISEN and CLAPAREDE, *B*, 14, 2464.
9. H. STOBBE and K. BREMER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1929, 123, 1.
10. POND and SHOFFSTALL, *Amer. Soc.*, 22, 666.
11. V. WALTHER and RATZE, *J. Pr(2)*, 65, 280.
12. A. RASSCHAERT, W. JANSSENS and P. J. SLOOTMAEKERS, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Belges*, 1966, 75, 449.
13. STOCKNAUSEN and GATTERMANN B, 25, 3536
14. R. B. SHENOI, R. C. SHAH and T. S. WHEELER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 247.
15. STAUS, A, 374, 139.
16. F. STAUS and H. BLANKENHORN, *Ann.*, 1918, 415, 292.
17. DILTNEY, *J. Pr(2)*, 101, 199.
18. R. B. KANTHI and K. S. NARGUND, *J. Karnatak Univ.*, 1957, 2, 8.

Synthesis of 1-formyl-8-hydroxycarbazole

S. MAJUMDAR, (MRS.) L. BHATTACHARYA
and

D. P. CHAKRABORTY

Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 10 July 1979, revised 23 April 1980,
accepted 5 November 1980

THE formyl carbazoles have recently figured prominently in carbazole alkaloids¹ as well as an intermediate in the synthesis of pyridocarbazoles of potential antitumour activity^{2,3}. Synthesis of carbazole aldehydes was first reported by Buu Hoi *et al*⁴, in 1951 and later by Tomlinson *et al*⁵, in 1957. Since there is no convenient and good method for the synthesis of formyl carbazoles, the present work for the synthesis of formyl carbazole was undertaken.

Chakraborty *et al*⁶, synthesised successfully many simple and complex carbazoles by Borsche method in conjunction with Japp-Klingemann reaction. Recently DDQ has been used to obtain formyl carbazoles from carbazoles with aromatic C-Me groups^{7,1}. We now report the synthesis of 1-formyl-8-hydroxycarbazole in which DDQ^{8,9}, has been used to effect aromatisation of six-membered aromatic ring with allyl alcoholic system and oxidation of the carbinol group in a single step.